

REMOTE WORK AND CLASS STRATIFICATION IN POST-COVID NIGERIA: A SOCIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the relationship between remote work and class stratification in post-COVID Nigeria from a sociological perspective. It argues that rather than democratising employment, remote work reproduces and intensifies existing class stratifications through unequal access to digital capital. Using Bourdieu's theory of capital and Marxist class analysis, the paper demonstrates that inequalities in internet access, infrastructure, educational attainment, occupational structure, and social networks significantly shape participation in remote work. While a small segment of digitally skilled professionals has accessed global labour markets and higher incomes, most workers remain excluded due to structural and occupational constraints. The paper concludes that remote work in Nigeria reinforces class stratification under digital capitalism, functioning as a mechanism of social reproduction of class stratification and inequality. It contributes to sociological debates on digital inequality in the Global South and offers policy implications for digital labour governance.

KEYWORDS: *Remote work, class stratification, digital labour, inequality, Bourdieu, COVID-19, digital divide*

RESEARCH ARTICLE

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic ushered in a tremendous transformation in the world of work. Lockdowns, physical distancing and restrictions on movement were measures put in place to curtail the spread of the virus. These measures made most organisations to adopt alternative work arrangements, notably, remote work (Al-Habaibeh et al., 2021; Imai et al., 2020). Remote work enabled workers to continue with their jobs, mostly from home, using digital technologies (Mariani et al., 2023). Research in the United States of America found that within weeks after the pandemic started, nearly 50% of all employed Americans were working remotely, and the shift was most pronounced in knowledge-based, professional and managerial occupations (Brynjolfsson et al., 2020). Beland et al. (2023) reported that individuals with the ability to work remotely were significantly less likely to experience job loss during the pandemic, compared to workers in occupations requiring physical presence such as plumbers, carpenters, bartenders, etc. While this shift was initially framed as a

temporary public health response, it has since become a permanent feature of the labour market, especially in societies with advanced digital infrastructure (Vyas, 2022; Raghavan et al., 2021).

Remote work is often associated with increased flexibility and expanded access to employment opportunities (Siegert., et al 2025). However, it has also reinforced existing inequalities and produced uneven social impacts (Cetrulo et al.,2022). In Nigeria, its adoption is marked by significant inequalities in access to critical infrastructure, such as electricity and internet connectivity, as well as in digital skills. Olanrewaju et al. (2021) observed that the COVID-19 pandemic exposed deep digital divides, particularly in rural areas. This reflects broader socio-economic inequalities that shape participation in remote work and digital labour markets.

This paper argues that remote work in post-COVID Nigeria tends to reinforce existing class divisions rather than diminish them. Instead of functioning as a leveller, the growth of remote work intensifies inequality by favouring individuals who possess the economic, cultural, and social capital necessary for participation in digital labour markets. According to Schradie (2020), viewing digital technology as inherently emancipatory hides the underlying class inequalities that influence its access and benefits. This study builds upon that perspective by applying it to the transformation of the Nigerian labour market while using Bourdieu's theory of capital and Marxist class analysis to examine how remote work constitutes a new dimension of class inequality in post-pandemic Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Remote Work and Labour Transformation

Remote work, variously referred to as telework, telecommuting, or working from home, has become a widely studied part of broader transformations in global labour markets (Elsamani et al., 2024; Braesemann et al., 2022; Skryl, 2021). According to Brynjolfsson et al. (2020), the transition to remote work largely favours workers in professional, managerial, and information-based occupations, whereas workers in sectors that depended on physical interaction experienced the sharpest declines in employment. Before the COVID-19 pandemic, remote work was largely a preserve of those in knowledge-based occupations such as information technology, consulting, finance, and digital services. Today, we now have people who work in remotely in administrative and support services as virtual assistants and customer service representatives. Some medical doctors now work remotely as telehealth physiciaans. In essence, COVID-19 pandemic dramatically accelerated the growth of remote work and transformed it from a niche arrangement to a mainstream mode of employment across multiple sectors and economies.

Studies have shown that remote work offers a range of organisational benefits, including greater flexibility, lower commuting costs, and enhanced collaboration among workers working across different locations (Galanti et al., 2021). Drawing on evidence from the United Kingdom, Adekoya et al. (2022) found that both employers and employees developed clear expectations regarding remote work, with flexibility, self-discipline, and digital literacy emerging as essential requirements for successful participation. Yet access to these opportunities remains uneven. Sostero et al. (2020) estimated that only 37% of jobs in the European Union can be effectively performed remotely, with telework opportunities concentrated among individuals with higher levels of education and occupational status. As a result, differences in access to remote work are not merely occupational in nature; they also reflect broader patterns of social class inequality.

Jobs that require physical presence, such as those in manufacturing, agriculture, transportation, retail, and construction, are largely incompatible with remote work arrangements. By contrast, professional and managerial roles are far more amenable to digitisation. Cetrulo et al. (2022) found that class-related characteristics, particularly levels of task autonomy and occupational hierarchy, are among the strongest predictors of teleworkability. They further show that workers unable to work remotely face higher risks of unemployment, lower earnings, and greater exposure to occupational hazards. This evidence positions remote work not simply as a technological option, but as a labour market resource whose distribution is deeply shaped by class structure.

2.2 Remote Work and Social Inequality

A growing body of research demonstrates that pre-existing inequalities in education, income, and occupational status profoundly shape access to remote work. Angelucci et al. (2020) found that, during the pandemic, job losses were up to three times greater for non-remote workers in the United States, and that this gap was larger than the differential impact on women, racial minorities, or workers without college degrees. This underscores the centrality of remote work capacity as a social stratification variable. Furthermore, research shows that the existence of racial inequalities in remote work in the United States (Asfaw, 2022). These inequalities are largely mediated by education and occupation, with four-year college attainment and occupational category explaining over 80% of the variation in the likelihood of teleworking between White and minority workers (Asfaw, 2022).

Income inequality reproduces unequal access to remote work in a self-reinforcing cycle. Individuals in higher income brackets are more capable of securing the technological infrastructure that digital labour depends on, including laptops, smartphones, stable internet connectivity, and backup power systems where needed. Xiang (2022) develops this argument through the concept of the “redistribution of mobility”, which implies how workers are differentially positioned in relation to remote work. He suggests that while some individuals have the autonomy to choose remote work, others are excluded from it altogether, and still others are compelled to adopt it.

Reuschke and Felstead (2020) reported that spatial inequalities played a significant role in shaping who could work remotely during the covid –19 pandemic. Urban dwelling, highly educated and high-income workers benefitted the most while rural, less educated and lower income workers were far less likely to do so. Most professionals held their jobs and income through remote work while many low-income and informal workers experienced devastating job losses and income shocks. Lenshie et al. (2021) documented how COVID-19 lockdowns devastated informal women workers in peri-urban communities in Nigeria. These women lacked both the digital infrastructure for remote work and the social protection mechanisms to cushion the loss of income. Abugamza et al. (2026) synthesised findings from 85 studies across multiple countries. They concluded that the pandemic systematically worsened pre-existing inequalities in employment, health, and income. The burden of these effects fell most heavily on women, less-educated workers, and those employed in high-contact and in-person occupations. These patterns lend substantial empirical support to the claim that remote work serves as a mechanism for reproducing social stratification and inequality.

2.3 Digital Divide and Inequality in Nigeria

In recent years, Nigeria has witnessed increased access to mobile telephony and internet penetration and use. However, there still exist a widespread and multilayered digital divide and inequality as access to dependable digital infrastructure remains deeply uneven (Chime 2023; Adeleke, 2021). Guo and Ogbodo (2026) found that material barriers, such as the cost

of devices and internet access, are significantly more expensive in Nigeria, and that rural populations are most affected. Similarly, Olanrewaju et al. (2021) observed that across six Nigerian states, weak connectivity, unreliable electricity, low socioeconomic status, and inadequate ICT policy frameworks drive digital exclusion. These conditions effectively marginalise rural communities from participation in the digital economy.

Digital inequality in Nigeria is also shaped by education and geography. Eke et al. (2025) found that urban institutions have more access to broadband internet than rural ones and that 65% of rural educators lack digital skills. Myovella et al. (2021) identified GDP, sociopolitical and economic stability, and social amenities as key factors in Africa's digital divide, linking access to broader development issues. These layered disadvantages create successive levels of inequality, where lack of access leads to skills gaps and unequal digital outcomes.

3. Theoretical Framework

3.1 Bourdieu's Theory of Capital and Digital Capital

Pierre Bourdieu's theory of capital analysed how inequality is produced and reproduced through uneven access to socially valued resources. Bourdieu (1986) distinguishes between economic capital, cultural capital, and social capital, each of which shapes individuals' life chances and positions within social fields. According to Flemmen et al. (2018), the theory remains relevant in understanding class differentiation in contemporary societies. They noted that the volume and composition of capital are still strong predictors of lifestyle differentiation and social position.

In the context of the digital economy, scholars have extended Bourdieu's framework to include digital capital (Ragnedda & Ruiu, 2020). This refers to individual-level technological skills and data-related competencies that are economically valuable yet unevenly distributed, thereby reproducing existing class structures. Building on this, Calderón Gómez (2020) uses Bourdieu's theory of capital to show how economic resources create barriers to digital participation. He argues that cultural capital is translated into digital form through processes of techno-socialisation, while social capital facilitates access through interpersonal and institutional networks. He further contends that digital capital can be reconverted into economic, cultural, and social capital, thereby reinforcing broader inequalities. In the context of remote work in Nigeria, economic capital includes access to computers, smartphones, internet subscriptions, and reliable electricity or backup power. Cultural capital refers to digital skills, technological competence, and educational qualifications that enable participation in online labour markets. Social capital, on the other hand, consists of professional networks, alumni associations, and informal ties that provide access to remote opportunities and referrals. These forms of capital are unevenly distributed in the Nigerian society and are largely concentrated among middle and upper-class groups. This shapes the boundaries of participation in digital labour markets. Leguina et al. (2021) further show that digital capital serves as a bridging resource that enhances the convertibility of other forms of capital, which ultimately benefits those who are already structurally advantaged.

3.2 Marxist Class Analysis and Digital Capitalism

From a Marxist perspective, class is defined in terms of people's relationship to the means of production. In the contemporary digital economy, digital infrastructure and digital skills have increasingly functioned as key productive resources, and control over them shapes workers' positions within emerging labour-market hierarchies (Muntaner, 2018). Digital platform capitalism reproduces the central class conflict over wages, benefits, and working conditions

that has long structured the relationship between capital and labour, even as forms of employment continue to evolve (Muntaner, 2018). The expansion of digital capitalism has also generated a “good gig, bad gig” dynamic, where the autonomy and flexibility of remote work are offset by low pay, social isolation, algorithmic control, and limited access to formal labour protections (Wood et al., 2019A). This dynamic is particularly pronounced in the Global South, where digital platforms intersect with pre-existing informality, weak regulation, and structural economic vulnerability. Gendered inequalities are also embedded in African digital platforms, with women facing economic insecurity, discrimination, and intensified work demands shaped by platform design (Anwar, 2022).

These patterns indicate that remote work reproduces capitalist class relations by benefiting digitally skilled, formally educated, and well-networked workers, while marginalising manual, informal, and less skilled labour. In Nigeria, this is reflected in the rise of a small digital professional class earning foreign currency through platforms like Upwork and Fiverr. This creates a new layer of class differentiation rather than replacing existing structures. This aligns with the argument that digital technologies do not erase inequality but tend to reproduce it through established class power differences (Schradie, 2020).

4. Remote Work and Class Stratification in Nigeria

4.1 Digital Capital and the Infrastructure of Inequality

Access to remote work in Nigeria is shaped by the unequal distribution of digital capital, encompassing the material resources and competencies needed to participate in digital labour markets. Middle and upper-income Nigerians are more likely to have laptops, stable internet, uninterrupted power, and the digital skills required for remote employment. Lower-income groups face compounding structural constraints that render remote work practically inaccessible. This stratification has deep material roots. Avordeh et al. (2024) found that power outages across Sub-Saharan Africa systematically reduces the operational capacity of small and medium enterprises, cutting productivity, raising costs, and perpetuating poverty. For individual remote workers, the same dynamics may hold, as reliable electricity is a prerequisite for digital labour and the inability to maintain power supply creates a structural barrier that closely maps onto class lines. Internet affordability worsens the electricity problem. Kemgou Kemgou Voptia and Stukalina (2025) report that although 84% of Sub-Saharan Africa’s population is within reach of 3G networks, fewer than 22% can afford mobile internet, with data costs consuming up to 10.5% of monthly income.

Remote work is not just about choice or motivation. It depends on digital infrastructure, which many Nigerian households can't afford. Middle-class households may be able to afford internet access, backup electricity generators, and digital devices. However, low-income households may not be able to afford these. This cycle links class to digital access, which in turn affects labour-market opportunities.

4.2 Occupational Stratification and Remote Work

Remote work is reshaping occupational stratification in Nigeria, even though it has not fundamentally eliminated existing inequalities. Historically, the Nigerian labour market has been characterised by a sharp divide between a relatively small formal sector that offers greater employment stability and a much larger informal sector marked by low wages and precarious working conditions (Folawewo, 2020). The expansion of remote work, including software development, digital marketing, virtual assistance, and online freelancing, has created new avenues for employment and income generation (Wood et al., 2019B). Yet access to these opportunities remain highly uneven. They are shaped by disparities in

educational attainment, digital competencies, and access to essential technological infrastructure such as reliable internet connectivity, electricity, and digital devices (Guo & Ogbodo, 2026).

These barriers confer significant advantages on individuals with higher levels of education, stronger language proficiency, and prior exposure to digital technologies. This positions them more favourably to secure remote employment, particularly in international labour markets (Braesemann et al., 2022). At the same time, persistent infrastructural deficiencies continue to constrain participation for large segments of the population, especially those living in rural areas and lower-income communities (Olanrewaju et al., 2021; Freundt et al., 2025).

Rather than eroding established patterns of inequality, remote work often reproduces them. Higher-skilled and better-remunerated remote positions tend to be concentrated among urban, middle-class workers, while lower-paid forms of gig work remain disproportionately accessible to more disadvantaged groups. In this way, remote work reproduces occupational stratification without eliminating it, reinforcing most of the social and occupational hierarchies already existing within the Nigerian labour market.

4.3 Urban-Rural Divide and Spatial Inequality

Urban centres such as Lagos, Abuja, and Port Harcourt benefit from comparatively better digital infrastructure. This enables higher rates of remote work participation among the educated urban professional class. Rural areas face severe infrastructural deficits that limit not only access to the internet but also educational attainment and occupational diversity. Crowley and Doran (2020) found that more affluent, densely populated, better-educated, and better-connected localities had significantly greater potential for remote work, while rural and deprived areas were structurally disadvantaged.

Digital infrastructure is mostly concentrated in urban areas, which creates a geographical layer of inequality in a labour market that is closely tied to class. Myovella et al. (2021) discovered that digital access in Sub-Saharan Africa is highly location-based. This suggests that the uneven spread of digital infrastructure means remote work opportunities are clustered in urban areas. This exacerbates the existing inequality and limits the upward mobility of workers in rural or peripheral localities.

4.4 Informal Labour Exclusion and Structural Vulnerability

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed the vulnerability of informal workers. In Nigeria, lockdown measures disrupted informal economic activities, reduced incomes, and weakened trade networks, while limited social protection left many workers without support (Lenshie et al., 2021). Similarly, Han et al. (2021) found that precarious employment increased the risk of income and job loss during the pandemic. As most informal occupations depend on physical presence, workers in this sector were largely excluded from remote work opportunities, further widening inequalities between them and the formally employed professional class. Nigeria's large informal sector, which accounts for most employment and livelihood activities, represents the most comprehensively excluded segment of the labour market from remote work opportunities. Most informal workers, such as petty traders, artisans, transport workers, domestic workers, and subsistence farmers, remain concentrated in occupations that require physical presence and direct interpersonal interaction. This may limit their ability to participate in remote work. ILO and OECD (2019) documented how informal workers are exposed to compounding poverty and occupational risks, with limited access to social protection or risk management mechanisms, rendering them acutely vulnerable to economic shocks.

5. Discussion

The empirical and theoretical review in this paper indicates that remote work in post-COVID Nigeria reproduces rather than transforms social inequalities. Instead of broadening access to work, it strengthens class divisions by favouring those already equipped with the necessary economic, cultural, and social capital for digital employment. This pattern reflects global trends but is intensified in Nigeria by weak infrastructure, a large informal economy, and entrenched class inequality.

The Bourdieusian framework applied in this paper highlights the interrelated mechanisms through which digital capital accumulation is structured by class position. Economic capital enables access to essential infrastructure such as devices, internet connectivity, and electricity. Cultural capital, reflected in educational attainment and digital literacy, shapes individuals' capacity to participate effectively in digital labour markets. Social capital, expressed through professional networks and alumni ties, facilitates access to remote work opportunities. In Nigeria, these forms of capital are unevenly distributed along class lines, producing cumulative disadvantages for lower-class workers. Calderón Gómez (2020) describes this process as bidirectional capital conversion, where existing economic, cultural, and social advantages are transformed into digital capital and subsequently reconverted into further economic gain.

From a Marxist perspective, remote work reflects and reproduces capitalist class relations in digital form. The emergence of a foreign-currency-earning digital professional class represents a new but structurally continuous form of inequality. Wood et al. (2019B) show that digital platforms intensify the commodification of labour through market-mediated work relations. In Nigeria, these dynamic benefits digitally connected professionals while excluding informal and rural workers, reinforcing labour market polarisation.

Zheng and Walsham (2021) propose an intersectional approach to digital inequality that moves beyond single-axis interpretations of the digital divide to examine how technology intersects with class, gender, race, and geography. This framework is highly relevant to Nigeria, where remote work inequalities overlap with gendered disparities in digital access, urban–rural divides, regional infrastructural inequalities, and generational gaps in digital literacy. In this context, the digital divide is a multidimensional phenomenon shaped by the historical legacies of uneven development, colonial economic structures, and post-independence socio-political dynamics.

From a policy standpoint, the analysis suggests that expanding remote work opportunities requires sustained, targeted investment in digital infrastructure, particularly in rural and peri-urban areas, alongside measures to improve electricity reliability and reduce internet access costs. Ehimuan et al. (2024) argue that context-specific digital inclusion strategies, encompassing investment in infrastructure, digital literacy programmes, and regulatory frameworks that promote affordable connectivity, are essential for bridging the digital divide in Nigerian contexts. Without such interventions, the expansion of remote work in Nigeria is likely to deepen rather than reduce class stratification, reinforcing the position of the digitally privileged while further marginalising the informally employed majority.

6. Conclusion

Remote work in post-COVID Nigeria reproduces rather than reduces class inequality, as access to remote labour markets is shaped by uneven distribution of economic, cultural, and social capital. While a small urban and educated segment benefits, most informal and rural workers remain excluded. Bourdieusian and Marxist frameworks show that digital capital

operates as a mechanism of class reproduction, requiring policy intervention to prevent further entrenchment of inequality. Future research should examine gendered, regional, and generational inequalities and track long-term outcomes of remote work participation.

Disclosure Statements

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